

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 93

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 93

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 93:1 ^aThe LORD ¹reigns, He is ^bclothed with majesty; The LORD has ^cclothed and girded Himself with strength; Indeed, the ^dworld is firmly established, it will not be moved. ² Your ^ethrone is established from of old; You ^bare from everlasting.</p> <p>Psa. 93:3 The ^afloods have lifted up, O LORD, The floods have lifted up their voice, The floods lift up their pounding waves. ⁴ More than the sounds of many waters, <i>Than</i> the mighty breakers of the sea, The LORD ^aon high is mighty. ⁵ Your ^atestimonies are fully confirmed; ^bHoliness befits Your house, O LORD, ¹forevermore.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 93:1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">יְהוָה מֶלֶךְ יִשְׂרָאֵל לְבִישׁ לְבָשׁ יְהוָה עֲזוֹ הַתְּאֵזָר אֶרְבֵּי-תְכוּן תְּכַל בַּלְתָּמוּט : ² נִכּוֹן כִּסְאֶךָ מֵאֵז מֵעוֹלָם אָתָּה : ³ נִשְׁאֵר נְהַרֹת יְהוָה נִשְׁאֵר נְהַרֹת קוֹלָם יִשְׁאֵר נְהַרֹת דְּכִיָּם : ⁴ מִקְלוֹת אֲמִים רַבִּים אֲדִירִים מִשְׁבְּרֵי-יָם אֲדִיר בַּמָּרוֹם יְהוָה : ⁵ עֵדוּתֶיךָ אֲנֵאמְנוּ מֵאֵד לְבֵיתְךָ נִאֲוָה-קִדְשׁ יְהוָה לְאַרְבַּע יָמִים :</p>

References

Psalm 93:1

¹Or *has assumed kingship*

^aPs 96:10; 97:1; 99:1

^bPs 104:1

^cPs 65:6; Is 51:9

^dPs 96:10

Psalm 93:2

^aPs 45:6; Lam 5:19

^bPs 90:2

Psalm 93:3

^aPs 96:11; 98:7, 8

Psalm 93:4

^aPs 65:7; 89:6, 9; 92:8

Psalm 93:5

¹Lit *for length of days*

^aPs 19:7

^bPs 29:2; 96:9; 1 Cor 3:17

Targum

Psa. 93:1 The LORD is king, he has put on greatness; the LORD has put on strength and girded himself; also he made strong the world, so that it will not be shaken. ² Your throne is established from the beginning; from eternity you are God. ³ The rivers lift up, O LORD, the rivers lift up their voice in song; the rivers will receive a reward for their praise. ⁴ The LORD is more to be praised in the highest heavens than the sound of many waters, the praiseworthy [waters], the breakers of the great sea! ⁵ Your testimonies are very true, beautiful and holy for your sanctuary, O LORD, for length of days.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The sage Rashi explained that this Psalm is dedicated to the Messianic era when all men will recognize the LORD's majesty again. It is a continuation of Psalm 92, which concluded with the prediction that people will declare the LORD just in the Messianic era. All humanity will recognize the LORD as the true God of Heaven and earth.

This Psalm is the song of the day for the sixth day of the week because the LORD completed his work on that day. Rav Yaakov Emden said this Psalm describes the LORD as robing himself in grandeur like one dressing in high Sabbath finery. On the sixth day, Adam was created. The LORD blew a breath of life into his nostrils and invested him with a Divine soul. As Adam sang praises to the LORD, he honestly looked Divine because he was a reflection of the LORD. All the creators of creation gathered to bow to him in submission because they thought Adam was their creator.

Verse three

"Floods" is a simile for powerful nations that swell with pride and work destruction in the world. These nations are hostile to the LORD's supremacy and have noisily raised their voices. In time they will be destroyed.

True, the floods, O LORD, the floods have lifted up their voices; the floods lift up their fall.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

